

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF REMOTE SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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In order to ensure the financial stability of banks and protect the interests of depositors and creditors, it is necessary to comply with prudential standards set by the Central Bank, and one of these prudential standards is the liquidity ratio, which determines the need to establish a reliable liquidity system in banks [1].

In recent years, constructive measures have been taken in the country to develop the banking system, in particular, the widespread introduction of modern IT technologies in the industry, the acceleration of the digitization process. The process has been accelerated since this year. This is not in vain. As the head of our state noted in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, "Unfortunately, the banking system lags behind modern requirements in the use of digital technologies, introduction of new banking products and software for 10-15 years [2].

In recent years, the country has been trying to increase the range of services provided to its customers and diversify its activities through the development of operations. To this end, banks are actively implementing electronic service technologies such as ATMs, mobile phones and remote management of their accounts via the Internet. Through the implementation of remote banking services, in addition to its traditional operations, the credit institution is also using new banking products that meet the needs of customers more fully and with better quality. But this is not enough, because in the rapidly evolving 21st century information technology age, there are still a number of problems related to real-time banking operations that need to be addressed [3].

Now let's get acquainted with the systems of remote servicing of bank accounts, remote servicing of accounts - these are the technologies of providing banking services on the basis of remote instructions (without visiting the bank). It is mainly done through computer and telephone networks. There are several types of remote accounts for bank accounts [4]:

Bank-Client is a computer-based system in which a special program is installed on the client's computer. This program stores all customer data on the computer (mainly payment documents and statements from accounts). There is a direct connection between the bank and the client's computer via a modem.

Internet-banking is a system that gives customers the right to manage their deposit accounts, including accounts opened with plastic cards, via the Internet. This type of service is a system designed to make real-time payments when the customer is remotely connected to the bank. The user logs in through a web browser [5].

The **Internet-banking** system will be hosted on the bank's web server. The user has the opportunity to view all their information (payment documents and statements from accounts) on the bank's website. Through the Internet-banking service, the client can do it at his workplace or in other convenient conditions:

- ↔ transfer of payments;
- ↔ monitoring of payment stages;
- ↔ Provides access to all operations at any time, such as receiving all reports.

Through Internet banking, the client will be able to connect to the bank's website from his workplace, see the money coming to his account, prepare money transfers and transfer them to the bank [6].

Mobile banking system is based on Internet banking technology.

SMS-banking is a bank deposit for customers is a system for receiving information in the form of SMS about transactions on accounts and accounts opened on plastic cards. To get information from the account, the client must send an SMS-request to a special telephone number of the bank [7].

SMS-banking service for the client allows you to perform the following actions:

- ⦿ funds received on the account;
- ⦿ expenses from the account;
- ⦿ account balance;
- ⦿ will be able to receive operational information on banking operations conducted during the day.

In general, in essence, the difference between traditional and remote banking service schemes of bank and customer communication is not very big. Both banking services and accounts have remained "in place", only the type of communication that "connects" the bank employee and customers has changed.

That is, transactions that can only be performed in a bank office, now can also be done remotely. The client can “rest on his feet” and not have to waste precious working time on the way to the bank building, claiming that he will perform a minute operation [8].

Types of remote banking services, such as customer banking, internet, telephone or mobile banking, despite their differences, have the following common advantages over traditional methods of customer service [9]:

- Improving the quality of service, the time limit will be removed through the remote banking service, ie the customer will be able to manage their account seven days a week, twenty-four hours a day [10];
- In addition to time constraints, the customer’s geographical location is also ignored [11].

Table 1

The number of users of remote banking systems as of April 1, 2022 [12]

№	Banks	Legal entities and individual entrepreneurs	Individuals	The total
1.	National Bank	80 460	1 359 900	1 440 360
2.	Industrial and Construction Bank of Uzbekistan	51 467	2 901 622	2 953 089
3.	Agrobank	172 635	3 346 099	3 518 734
4.	Ipoteka-bank	135 695	1 919 510	2 055 205
5.	Mikrokreditbank	52 619	755 103	807 722
6.	Xalq bank	71 908	3 090 144	3 162 052
7.	Merchant bank	8 636	81 772	90 408
8.	Rural construction bank	24 616	370 100	394 716
9.	Turonbank	29 501	245 870	275 371
10.	Partner bank	98 942	1 300 718	1 399 660
11.	Asaka bank	35 191	923 367	958 558
12.	Silk Road Bank	40 738	1 086 723	1 127 461
13.	Ziraat bank Uzbekistan	2 571	34 526	37 097
14.	Trastbank	34 665	172 011	206 676
15.	Contact bank	45 257	491 330	536 587
16.	KDB Bank	938	37 780	38 718

	Uzbekistan			
17.	Turkistonbank	3 786	15 741	19 527
18.	Soderot bank Toshkent	243	1 793	2 036
19.	Universal bank	8 399	99 127	107 526
20.	Kapitalbank	35 191	353 511	388 702
21.	Ravnaqbank	2 255	46 787	49 042
22.	Davr-bank	22 183	93 773	115 956
23.	Invest Finance bank	24 772	366 885	391 657
24.	Asia Alliance bank	14 888	236 881	251 769
25.	Hi-Tech bank	1 618	22 179	23 797
26.	Orient Finans bank	25 247	365 800	391 047
27.	Madad Invest bank	914	2 531	3 445
28.	Uzagroeksportbank	56	1 286	1 342
29.	Poytaxt bank	851	4 885	5 736
30.	Tenge bank	813	12 783	13 596
31.	TBC bank	0	478 275	478 275
32.	ANOR bank	7 082	801 442	808 524
The total		1 034 137	21 020 254	22 054 391

The table above shows the number of users of Remote Banking Systems of commercial banks operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan, with 80,460 legal users and 1,359,900 individuals at the expense of the National Bank. The total number of users in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 1,034,137 legal users and 21,020,254 physical users. The total number of users is 22,054,391. From this we can say that the number of users of banking services in Uzbekistan is growing from year to year, which, along with a sharp increase in demand for banking services, leads to development competition between banks.

Table 2

Analytical information on payments made through the Central Bank's Instant Payment System [13]

billion soums

№	Name of banks	Payments received during March 2022		Including the budget	
		<i>number</i>	<i>amount</i>	<i>number</i>	<i>amount</i>
1.	National Bank	170	5 470 819	20	338 911

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		602	272 356	605	427 391
2.	Self-governing bank	101 363	4 473 516 326 946	13 531	114 710 657 716
3.	Agrobank	12 287	425 537 408 547	634	18 855 972 838
4.	Mikrokreditbank	86 626	758 537 406 004	28 324	20 011 660 886
5.	Xalq bank	154 870	1 493 352 335 153	67 060	92 621 117 543
6.	Merchant bank	19 341	260 823 288 529	2 050	3 119 188 330
7.	Rural construction bank	118 833	1 263 424 533 860	55 132	62 519 633 649
8.	Turonbank	39 287	841 469 807 079	3 429	10 187 481 601
9.	Partner bank	100 035	2 625 364 872 029	12 554	34 421 340 984
10.	Asaka bank	69 161	4 499 616 725 615	15 437	145 077 302 923
11.	Silk Road Bank	15 386	506 448 506 205	3 197	43 089 980 440
12.	Ziraat Bank Uzbekistan	696	41 534 423 008	42	1 926 001 118
13.	Trastbank	63 246	1 445 787 082 099	9 667	26 487 170 493
14.	Contact bank	78 356	941 439 103 322	6 114	136 189 923 154
15.	Ipoteka-bank	36 941	1 292 543 773 649	3 481	116 792 109 052

It should be noted that the information services of Uzbekistan are developing rapidly, their total volume has increased by 4.6 times. The implementation of programs for the development of telecommunications networks, computerization and information technology is leading to the growth of wireless telephone communications, an increase in the number of mobile subscribers and public access points to the Internet [14].

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